

Leveraging Healthcare Policy for Climate Action: Medicaid's Underutilized Potential

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Abstract

Climate change is a local, national, and global public health crisis. Increased extreme weather variations, heat waves, climate-related displacement, morbidity due to pollution, mental health conditions, and infectious disease transmission are mere examples of current and future impacts on population health. State Medicaid agencies have a unique opportunity to catalyze change in health policy that can address local and national needs for climate action. Medicaid Section 1115 demonstration waivers, for example, may be used to fund innovative projects to support those affected by extreme weather conditions. Expanding telehealth coverage may provide continuity of care for patients unable to access in-person services, while reducing greenhouse gas emissions on physical clinical space and transportation. State Medicaid agencies may financially incentivize the monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions by individual healthcare facilities, further encouraging transparent quality improvement metrics to identify future innovations on a local scale. Leveraging Medicaid's health policy reach to support climate action addresses the healthcare sector's responsibility to reduce contributions to climate change while creating initiatives that support population health for those acutely affected. In recognizing the disproportionate burden that climate change places on the health of marginalized groups, these health policy actions are prudent and necessary.

Introduction

Population Health & Climate Change

Climate change is one of the most pressing population health crises of our time. In North America, more than 191,000 deaths per year are related to extreme weather variations. [1,2]In 2021, a one-week heat wave caused 600 deaths in Washington and Oregon alone.[3] Worsening air pollution from wildfires has been linked to greater acute hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory disease.[4] Exposure to wildfires during pregnancy is associated with worse birth outcomes.[5] In 2020, greater air particulate matter from wildfires was found to increase COVID-19-related deaths across the western United States.[6] Vector-borne disease spread is also amplified. A recent systematic review found that transmission of 218 out of 375 infectious diseases affecting humans are directly affected by climate change.[7] Global warming, precipitation changes, and environmental habitat expansions are associated with increased outbreaks of Zika[8], malaria[8], dengue[8], trypanosomiasis, and plague.[11,9]

Evidence of climate change's effects on mental health are apparent. Individuals with direct experiences with flooding are more likely to experience depression and anxiety.[10] Children exposed to natural disasters are more likely to have long-term mental health consequences.[11–13] [77]For both acute and long-term health outcomes, the need to address climate change is clear.

The Role of Health Policy

US healthcare is a major contributor to environmental damage. A 2020 analysis showed that greenhouse gas emissions from US health care reached 1,692 kg per capita in 2018, contributing to the loss of 388,000 disability-adjusted-life-years in one year alone.[14] Sources of the sector's greenhouse gas emissions include healthcare facilities, such as on-site boilers and maintenance electricity, and supply-chain emissions from production, transportation, and storage of medical equipment.[14] The healthcare sector is responsible for 8.5% of the nation's greenhouse gas emissions.[14] Globally, US healthcare is responsible for one-quarter of all global healthcare-related greenhouse gas emission.[15] US healthcare policy has a responsibility to leverage its resources to catalyze change for environmental health.

The United States, like other countries, has begun to make policy changes that address this opportunity. In 2022, the Biden Administration announced the Health Sector Climate Pledge – a plan to halve healthcare-related greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.[16] 61 healthcare entities, including both public and private hospital organizations, the Department of Veterans (VA), medical device suppliers, and over 200 federal hospitals and facilities from the DHHS pledged their commitment.[16]

Section 1115 Demonstrations

The large purchasing power of Medicaid in healthcare facilities, as well as its state-wide regulatory capacity, can catalyze greater change.[17]For example, state Medicaid agencies can receive multi-year funding for innovative projects through Department of Health and Human Services Section 1115 Demonstration waivers. State agencies may submit a proposal aimed to support their local beneficiaries in a topic of interest for the state. In this way, Medicaid agencies may use Section 1115 funding to build innovative projects that support both Medicaid beneficiaries and climate action.[18]

Oregon's Section 1115 Demonstration waiver provides housing, climate, and nutrition support for those who face extreme weather events across the state.[19] In this program, Oregon Health Plan (OHP) members can receive extra air conditioners, air filters, backup power sources to operate medical devices (i.e. ventilators), and mini refrigerators to store medications, during climate-related emergencies.[19] Many medications – including antibiotics and insulin – may not be safe to use without proper refrigeration, making this initiative essential in mitigating climate disaster-related impacts on routine health maintenance.

In addition to reducing disruptions to medication adherence, preventing acute heat stroke, and reducing pollution-related respiratory conditions, this innovative program has the potential to address

climate action through an equitable lens. OHP members who were released from incarceration in the last 12 months, are currently or previously involved with the state's child welfare system, or are unhoused, automatically qualify for these devices.[19] In this way, Oregon's innovative program addresses the links between population health equity and climate change. Climate emergencies are known to exacerbate racial disparities in health outcomes. Climate-change events, such as heatwaves, floods, and wildfires, disproportionately affect Black, Latinx, Native American, Pacific Islander, and Asian communities.[20] Oregon's use of the Section 1115 Medicaid waiver both supports healthcare facilities in times of climate-related emergency while supporting the population health through a lens of public health justice.

Expanding Telehealth

Outside of Section 1115 waivers, State Medicaid agencies can be catalysts for climate action by supporting telehealth and encouraging transparent sustainability data in healthcare delivery.[21] The COVID-19 pandemic allowed certain healthcare services to be delivered virtually, as many state Medicaid agencies began to cover telehealth for beneficiaries.[21] In North Carolina, for example, pandemic-related legislature allowed Medicaid reimbursement for telehealth psychiatric diagnostic appointments and psychotherapy.[22] Although not all medical appointments are appropriately suited for virtual visits, expanding the use of telehealth can provide greater continuity of care and may reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transportation and office use for patients and providers alike.[21] A recent systematic review found that travel-associated greenhouse gas emission savings 'significantly outweighed the carbon footprint of telehealth equipment', estimating that telehealth visits reduced carbon dioxide emissions by 0.70 to 372 kg per visit.[23]

Monitoring Quality Improvement

To monitor their progress on healthcare-related greenhouse gas emissions, state Medicaid agencies can leverage financial incentives for quality improvement metrics. In Washington State, the Medicaid Quality Incentive provides healthcare facilities with a percent-financial incentive for completing a survey on their direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions.[24,25] Participating hospitals are then asked to collaborate with teams on goals to address improvements.[25] In this way, the state Medicaid agency is able to collect facility-level information on climate action progress to guide future policies. At a national level, opportunities for increasing quality improvement metrics are vast. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services Decarbonization and Resilience Initiative will invite acute care hospitals to report data on organizational, building energy, anesthetic gas, and transportation emissions from 2026 until 2030.[26] Hospitals may then opt-in to receive individualized feedback, compare progress with other facilities, and have the ability to receive national recognition for their improvements.[26]

Conclusion

State Medicaid agencies face a unique opportunity to support the public health of their beneficiaries by leveraging healthcare policy to address climate action. Through Section 1115 waivers, innovative projects, and transparent quality improvement monitoring, Medicaid can use its vast resources to address healthcare's burden on climate change. In doing so, policies can equitably improve environmental and population health alike.

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